

Estimation of Thiosemicarbazide and Its Metal Complexes with Lead Tetra Acetate

B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasa Gangotri, Mysore-570006.

Manuscript received 14 June 1976, revised 12 December 1976, accepted 30 December 1976.

A simple but accurate method for the estimation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) and its 'ionic' and 'neutral' complexes with Zn, Cd, Hg, Co, Ni, Pt and Pd, by lead tetra acetate, in aqueous or pH 4 buffer medium containing KBr and sodium acetate has been developed. The direct titration with a visual or potentiometric end point involves generally a 11 electron change per molecule of the TSC in the pure state and in its complexes. The platinum complexes are however oxidized with a 9-electron change per molecule of the ligand. A back titration procedure in which TSC and its complexes in aqueous or pH 4 buffer medium are oxidized by lead tetra acetate with a 10-electron change per ligand molecule has also been developed. The proposed analytical methods are useful for a rapid estimation of TSC and its complexes on a macro scale and also for computing the number of ligand molecules in a TSC metal complex.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (TSC) is well known as a metal complexing agent and also finds application in the characterization of aldehydes, ketones and polysaccharides. TSC derivatives are antitubercular active and are found to be active against influenza, protozoa, small pox and certain kinds of tumour. They have also been suggested as possible pesticides and fungicides. Their activity has been thought to be due to their ability to chelate trace metals. These facts have led recently to an increased interest in the chemistry of transition metal chelates of thiosemicarbazides.^{1,2} Since a number of metal complexes of the compound are known, suitable analytical techniques are essential for estimating TSC in the free state as well as in its complexes. The methods reported for its estimation so far are based on its oxidation by alkali metal hypohalites^{3,4} and organic⁵⁻⁸ chloramines.

Lead tetra acetate (LTA or PbAc₄) is a versatile oxidant, commonly employed as a reagent in preparative organic chemistry. The redox potential of Pb⁴⁺/Pb²⁺ is about 1.40 v in presence of perchloric acid and is about 1.30 v in presence of sodium acetate. Although the reaction of LTA with pure TSC has been mentioned in literature⁹, detailed studies are lacking. During the oxidation of some thiols with LTA, Suchomelova and Zyka⁹ have reported a back titration method in which TSC undergoes a 10-electron oxidation with LTA. However the method is sluggish (2-5 mg. oxidized in 2 hours' time) and is limited to the estimation of very small quantities. Further, this back titration procedure involves a potentiometric end point.

In the present investigations, rapid and accurate analytical techniques have been proposed for estimating TSC and its complexes with zinc group of metals

and cobalt, nickel, platinum and palladium, by LTA. The proposed methods include (i) a direct titration between the reductants and LTA in presence of potassium bromide and sodium acetate, with a visual or potentiometric end point and (ii) a back titration procedure in presence of sodium acetate.

Materials and Methods

E'Merck thiosemicarbazide was purified by recrystallization from aqueous solution. PdCl₂ and H₂PtCl₆·x H₂O (Johnson-Matthey Ltd., London) were used for preparing the Pt(II) and Pd(II) complexes. Triply distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. Lead tetra acetate (Riedel) was used without further purification. An approximately decinormal solution of the compound in glacial acetic acid was prepared, standardised by the iodometric method and stored in an amber coloured bottle. All other materials and reagents were of accepted grades of purity. A Bajaj potentiometer with a platinum indicator electrode and a reference calomel electrode was used for potentiometric titrations. UV spectra were obtained from a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded on a Carl Zeiss UR-10 Infrared spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Complexes

Thiosemicarbazide (L) complexes of zinc, cadmium, mercury, nickel, cobalt, platinum and palladium were prepared as follows :

Zinc group Complexes : ML₂X₂ where M = Zn, Cd or Hg, X = Cl, NO₃, ClO₄ or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄ were prepared by methods described in the previous communications.¹⁰

Nickel and Cobalt complexes: Preparation of $\text{NiL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ have been reported.^{5,6} NiL_2Cl_2 was prepared by mixing aqueous solution of TSC and $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the stoichiometric ratio and evaporating in a vacuum desiccator. The neutral complex $\text{Ni}(\text{L-H})_2^*$ was obtained¹¹ by direct reaction of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and TSC in aqueous ammonia in 1 : 2 mole ratio. $\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was obtained¹² by the interaction of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and TSC in the ratio 1 : 3 in presence of conc. HNO_3 or a saturated solution of NaNO_3 .

Platinum and Palladium complexes^{13,14}: *Cis*- PtL_2Cl_2 was prepared by mixing $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and TSC in hot ethanol in slightly beyond 1 : 2 mole ratio, while the *trans* compound was obtained by mixing the reactants in cold condition. *Cis*- $\text{PtL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, *trans*- PtL_2Br_2 , *trans*- PtL_2I_2 , *trans*- $\text{PtL}_2(\text{CN})_2$ and *trans*- $\text{PtL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ were prepared by anion substitution, by adding stoichiometric amounts of saturated aqueous solutions of the respective nitrate (or 1 : 1 HNO_3) or halide or cyanide or thiocyanate to an ice cold saturated aqueous solution of *Cis*- PtL_2Cl_2 . *trans*- PdL_2Cl_2 was prepared by mixing PdCl_2 and the ligand in 1 : 2 mole ratio in 2M HCl. *trans*- $\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, *trans*- PdL_2Br_2 , *trans*- PdL_2I_2 , *cis*- $\text{PdL}_2(\text{CN})_2$ and *cis*- $\text{PdL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ were prepared by methods similar to those of the corresponding platinum complexes. *Cis*- $\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ could also be precipitated by mixing $\text{Pd}(\text{OH})_2$ and TSC (in 1 : 2 mole ratio) in 1 : 1 HNO_3 at 60–70°. The neutral complexes, *trans*- $\text{Pt}(\text{L-H})_2$ and *trans*- $\text{Pd}(\text{L-H})_2$ were prepared respectively by the addition of excess 1 M ammonia to aqueous solutions of the corresponding chloride complex.

The complexes were recrystallised from aqueous solution and their composition was checked by elemental analyses.

Pt and Pd complexes were found to be diamagnetic, as expected for the square-planar complexes. Conductance measurements on aqueous solution (10^{-3} M) of ionic complexes showed that they are 1 : 2 electrolytes. UV spectra of the complexes show an intraligand band around 43 kK, while a charge transfer band (from sulphur to metal) is found around 37 kK. A common band at 28.5 kK is attributed to a d-d transfer, characteristic of square planar complexes.

The nature of metal-ligand bonding in the complexes was established¹⁴ by comparing their IR spectra with the spectrum of TSC. This compound has N-H stretching frequencies at 3389, 3285 and 3194 cm^{-1} . On complexation the bands at 3389 and 3194 cm^{-1} slightly shift to lower frequencies, while a small upper shift is noticed with the 3285 cm^{-1} band. The strong band at 800 cm^{-1} in TSC attributed to pure C=S stretch shifts to lower regions by as much as 100 cm^{-1} in the complexes. It is likely that the metal ion coordinates through both the nitrogen atom of the hydrazinic residue and sulphur atom of the ligand.

* (L-H) represents $\text{NH}_2\text{NCSNH}_2$.

Cis and *trans* isomers among the complexes were classified by the differences in their I.R. spectra^{13,14}. X-ray diffraction studies showed that, due to absence of symmetry, the *cis* form shows more line than the *trans* form.

Solution of TSC and its complexes were prepared in aqueous medium or in pH 4 acetate buffer (2 mg/ml).

1. Direct titration :

(a) *With visual end point* : A direct titration of TSC and its complexes with LTA was found practicable in the presence of sodium acetate and KBr, the former to accelerate the decomposition of LTA. The oxidant liberates bromine from KBr, which in turn oxidises TSC or its complex while at the same time serving as an indicator to detect the end point in an Andrews type of titration, employing carbon tetrachloride. Addition of a small quantity of ZnSO_4 solution was essential in the titration of pure TSC with LTA.

Recommended procedure : Take aliquots of TSC or its complex (~2-50 mg) in a 100 ml conical flask. Add 5 ml of 20% sodium acetate, 5 ml of 10% KBr and 1 ml of CCl_4 (5 ml of 10% ZnSO_4 solution in case of pure TSC). Titrate against LTA with shaking till the appearance of a faint yellow colour in CCl_4 layer.

Blank correction is found to be about 0.1 ml of 0.1 N LTA.

(b) *Potentiometric end point* : A potentiometric titration of TSC and its complexes with LTA was possible in presence of sodium acetate (5 ml of 20% solution) and KBr (5 ml of 10% solution). A large potential jump of 300-500 mV was noticed for the addition of 0.1 ml of 0.1 N oxidant at the equivalence point. In the absence of KBr no potential break was found in most cases while small potential jumps of the order of 100 mV occurred with a few complexes, which however did not correspond to any definite stoichiometry. Addition of a small quantity of zinc sulphate (5 ml of 10% solution) was essential in the titration of pure TSC with LTA.

2. Back titration method :

Preliminary investigations : In preliminary investigations known amounts of TSC or complex solution were added to a known excessive volume of LTA (~50-60% excess) also containing sodium acetate (5 ml of 20% solution) in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time at room temperature with occasional shaking. The excess LTA left unconsumed was iodometrically determined by back titration with standard sodium thiosulphate.

Oxidation of TSC with LTA was sluggish and required about an hour but addition of 5 ml of 10% zinc sulphate was found to catalyse the oxidation. Stoichiometric oxidation of TSC with a 10-electron change took place within 30 minutes. Complexes of TSC except those of Pt and Pd could be oxidized by LTA with 10-electron stoichiometry per molecule of ligand within 5 minutes. The same stoichiometry is shown by Pt and Pd complexes in the durations shown below :

Cis-PtL₂Cl₂, *trans*-PtL₂Cl₂, PtL₂Br₂ and PtL₂I₂ (3 hrs) ; Pt(L-H)₂ and PtL₂(NO₃)₂ (4 hrs) ; PtL₂(CN)₂, PtL₂(CNS)₂ (5 hrs) ; PdL₂Cl₂, PdL₂Br₂ and PdL₂I₂ (2 hrs) ; PdL₂(NO₃)₂ and Pd(L-H)₂ (3 hrs) ; PdL₂(CNS)₂ (4 hrs).

Recommended procedure : Prepare a solution of TSC or its complex (~2 mg/ml) in water or pH 4 buffer. Add aliquots of the solution to a known excessive volume of 0.1N LTA (~50-60%) in an iodine flask also containing 5 ml of 20% sodium acetate (in the case of TSC, 5 ml of 10% ZnSO₄ should be added). Shake the contents and set aside for the

duration mentioned above. Add 10 ml of each of 20% potassium iodide and 20% sodium acetate solutions. Titrate the liberated iodine against 0.1 N sodium thio-sulphate. Run a blank with LTA alone.

Results and Discussion

The results of analyses are shown in table 1. The values are found to be within 1% error.

Direct titration : Generally TSC in the pure state and in its metal complexes is oxidized with a 11-electron change per molecule under these conditions, with the exception of platinum complexes and PdL₂I₂. The 11-electron stoichiometry is shown as follows :

However, PdL₂I₂ is oxidized with a 26 electron change per complex molecule corresponding to the formation of Pd (CNO)₂.

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (TSC) AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES WITH LEAD TETRAACETATE

Compound	Taken	Range studied (mg)		
		Direct titration	Found	
			Visual end point	Potentiometric end point
TSC(L)	2.07-62.10	2.09-61.75	2.06-61.73	2.08-61.73
ZnL ₂ SO ₄	2.11-52.77	2.13-52.31	2.12-52.40	2.12-52.70
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	2.09-52.35	2.10-52.08	2.09-52.09	2.09-52.27
ZnL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.05-51.15	2.03-51.39	2.03-51.14	2.06-51.27
ZnL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	2.08-52.08	2.10-52.15	2.10-52.04	2.09-51.80
CdL ₂ SO ₄	2.03-50.62	2.03-50.74	2.03-50.66	2.05-50.64
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	2.06-51.50	2.08-51.53	2.07-51.36	2.08-51.30
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	2.03-50.69	2.03-50.83	2.02-50.63	2.01-50.61
<i>Cis</i> -PtL ₂ Cl ₂	2.11-52.85	2.11-52.56	2.11-52.50	2.10-52.63
<i>trans</i> -PtL ₂ Cl ₂	1.06-31.86	1.06-31.97	1.06-31.91	1.05-31.73
PtL ₂ Br ₂	1.78-31.15	1.79-31.22	1.79-31.14	1.80-31.17
PtL ₂ I ₂	1.27-38.10	1.28-38.19	1.26-37.99	1.27-37.90
PtL ₂ (CN) ₂	1.02-30.65	1.01-30.69	1.02-30.60	1.01-30.53
PtL ₂ (CNS) ₂	1.11-33.18	1.12-33.19	1.10-33.09	1.11-33.13
PtL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.35-43.46	1.34-40.58	1.34-40.24	1.34-40.52
Pt(L-H) ₂	2.75-40.34	2.76-41.36	2.77-41.47	2.77-41.38
PdL ₂ Cl ₂	1.34-33.59	1.34-33.27	1.33-33.18	1.33-33.47
PdL ₂ Br ₂	1.70-29.74	1.71-29.80	1.69-29.68	...
PdL ₂ I ₂	1.20-30.00	1.20-30.06	1.19-29.99	1.20-29.93
PdL ₂ (CNS) ₂	1.36-30.51	1.35-30.56	1.37-30.26	1.35-30.30
<i>Cis</i> -PdL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.32-39.47	1.33-39.71	1.31-39.40	1.33-39.45
<i>trans</i> -PdL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.32-39.59	1.34-39.66	1.31-39.60	1.30-39.60
Pd(L-H) ₂	1.79-44.79	1.79-44.85	1.79-44.60	1.78-44.62
CoL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.30-57.39	2.29-57.69	2.29-57.46	2.32-57.16
NiL ₂ SO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	2.11-52.88	2.13-52.61	2.09-52.61	2.10-52.63
NiL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.11-52.70	2.11-52.85	2.11-52.68	2.12-52.69
NiL ₂ Cl ₂	1.88-56.28	1.89-56.19	1.89-56.08	1.87-56.11
Ni(L-H) ₂	2.04-50.96	2.02-50.54	2.02-50.46	2.04-50.98

Pt-complexes with the exception of $PtL_2(CN)_2$ are oxidized with a 9-electron change per ligand molecule while the latter shows a 11-electron change per TSC molecule.

Back titration: The ligand in the pure state and in the complexes is oxidized with a 10-electron change as per the following stoichiometry

No definite stoichiometry was obtained for PdL_2Br_2 under these conditions. Although the cobalt complex $CoL_3(NO_3)_3$ is oxidized by LTA with a 30-electron change per molecule of the complex (liberation of one equivalent of iodine by Co^{3+} has been excluded) in pH 4 buffer medium, no definite stoichiometry was obtained in aqueous solution.

Attempts were made to detect the products of oxidation. The cyanide ion and cyanogen were detected by spot tests.¹⁶

It was noticed that the CNS^- ion present in Pt and Pd complexes is also oxidized by the oxidant¹⁵ under these conditions (both in direct and back titration procedures) with a 12-electron change per molecule of the complex. Allowance was made for this fact in calculating the amount of complex recovered.

Common anions such as SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- do not interfere in the estimation but KCN and KI interfere in direct titration and KCl and KBr in back titration. However, N_2H_4 and KCNS interfere in both the methods. It was found that presence of water and alkali acetate accelerates the rate of oxidation while a retardation effect is observed when solutions of TSC in glacial acetic acid are used.

It can be concluded from the above investigations that the analytical methods suggested are fairly rapid and accurate and are useful for estimating macro quantities of the ligand in the pure state and in its

complexes by a proper adjustment of reaction conditions. Also, an approximate computation of the number of ligand molecules present in a TSC complex can be made by these analytical techniques.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.T.G.) acknowledges financial assistance from the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, in the form of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. M. A. ALI and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 13, 101.
2. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 15, 279.
3. A. GAFFRE in 'Volumetric Analysis', I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, Interscience, New York, 1957 Vol. 3, p. 386.
4. J. PLUCK, A. CAMPE and A. CLAEYS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges*, 1964, 73, 898.
5. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Talanta*, 1970, 17, 431.
6. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1972, 41, 100.
7. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and B. T. GOWDA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 306.
8. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976 45, 161.
9. L. SUCHOMELOVA and J. ZYKA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, 5, 57.
10. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 1565.
11. M. CAVALCA, M. NARDELLI and G. FAVA, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1962, 15, 1139.
12. M. K. AKHMEDLI and A. M. SADYKHOVA, *Azerb. Khim. Zh.* 1963 (4), 141, through *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 1488.
13. R. A. HAINES and K. K. W. SUN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, 46, 3241.
14. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 985.
15. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and B. T. GOWDA, unpublished results.
16. F. FEIGL, 'Spot tests in Inorganic Analysis', p. 285, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1958.